

CLASSROOM FACTORS THAT IMPACT STUDENT NEGATIVE DISPOSITIONS

TOWARD MATHEMATICS: CONSIDERATIONS FOR EQUITY

by

Natalie Coria

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9180-6573

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6654093

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton

May 2022

Approved by:

Dr. Mark Ellis, Department of Secondary Education

Dr. Yuying Tsong, Director University Honors Program

Date:

30 May 2022

5/31/2022

Abstract

Education is an exciting topic and a vital one as it is through education that the generations to come are developing the knowledge, skills, and dispositions necessary for their adult lives. As a future mathematics teacher, I chose to do a literature review on mathematics education and its role in misshaping student dispositions toward mathematics. I found that traditional approaches and perspectives toward mathematics teaching that over-emphasize rote learning and devalue students' mathematical reasoning and sense-making have contributed to a negative disposition toward mathematics among many people, disproportionately among those from less privileged backgrounds. As society has become more technology-dependent and data-driven, we must improve the way mathematics is taught and provide students with all the resources they need to be active participants in a society reliant upon mathematical algorithms and mathematical reasoning. I review the effects of specific components of mathematics education that shape student dispositions and highlight more effective and equitable practices. To check the impact of mathematical dispositions, I reviewed scholarly publications explicitly focusing on the roots of negative dispositions toward mathematics through the lens of secondary school students and how they affect the quality of learning mathematics. The conclusion will highlight the characteristics of more productive practices of teaching mathematics that combat the roots of negative dispositions.

Contents

Introduction	4
The Roots of Negative Dispositions Toward Mathematics	9
Negative Root 1: Instrumental Learning Goals & Misuse of Assessment	9
Negative Root 2: Lack of Student Engagement & Negative Class Climate	13
Negative Root 3: Fixed Mindset about Ability	19
Combating the Negative Roots Toward Equitable Outcomes	22
Positive Root 1: Relational Learning Goals & Advantageous Use of Assessment	25
Positive Root 2: Increasing Student Engagement & Setting a Positive Class Climate	29
Positive Root 3: Supporting the Growth Mindset	33
Conclusion	37
Appendix	40
Table 1	40
Table 2	41
References	42

Introduction

Mathematics proficiency is lacking among students in both secondary and post-secondary schools, as revealed by the outcomes of high school assessments of mathematics knowledge and the high failure and withdrawal rates in introductory post-secondary mathematics courses. Data from the 2020-21 California state mathematics assessment show that by grade eleven while barely one-third of students are demonstrating proficiency, only about one-fifth of Latinx, Black, and low-income students are demonstrating proficiency, and fewer than one-tenth of students designated as English learners are demonstrating proficiency ([California Department of Education, n.d.](#)). And post-secondary outcomes are not much better. Specifically, one of the courses with the highest failure and withdrawal rate is College Algebra, the lowest level college mathematics credit-bearing course. For example, data from California State University Los Angeles during 2018 – 2021 show that Modern Algebra I (MATH 4550) had a 41.1% failure and withdrawal rate ([Allen, as cited in Gordon, 2021](#)). As a result, many students lack introductory algebra knowledge and skills needed for upper-division mathematics courses – i.e., Calculus – leading to high upper-division mathematics course failure and withdrawal rates ([Gordon, 2022](#)). As [Gordon \(2021\)](#) surmises in an article about college mathematics failure rates:

Challenging course material, ineffective teaching and unprepared or overwhelmed students contribute to the rise in high failure/withdrawal rates, experts say. Failures and repeated attempts to pass can add semesters to students' time on campus because many of the courses are required for majors. Worse, failing a class can send students into a tailspin that leads to abandoning majors or dropping out altogether. ([para. 7](#))

Considering that many students struggle with mathematics starting in secondary school (from grade seven), I focus my investigation on secondary mathematics education. If we improve

secondary mathematics education, we may be able to lessen the failure and withdrawal rates in post-secondary mathematics education.

While looking at outcomes gives a sense of the problem, in order to effect change, it is necessary to identify and address the root causes for these outcomes. Reading how mathematical proficiency is defined by researchers [Kilpatrick, Swafford, and Findell \(2001\)](#), I learned that there are five intertwined strands that together capture what a person knows and can do within the discipline: (1) procedural fluency, (2) conceptual understanding, (3) adaptive reasoning, (4) strategic competence, and (5) productive disposition. As pointed out by [Grady \(2016\)](#), the first four strands are emphasized in the *Common Core State Standards for Mathematics (CCSSM)*, which form the basis for California's standards in mathematics. However, the fifth strand – productive disposition – lacks explicit emphasis in state standards. This means that while much attention has been given to supporting teachers and students with the first four strands of mathematical proficiency, much less has been paid to productive disposition. This is unfortunate since it is dispositions that have a large impact on the ways students respond to challenges in mathematics and make decisions about their identity toward mathematics. According to [Kilpatrick, Swafford, and Findell \(2001\)](#):

Students' disposition toward mathematics is a major factor in determining their educational success. Students who view their mathematical ability as fixed and test questions as measuring their ability rather than providing opportunities to learn are likely to avoid challenging problems and be easily discouraged by failure. Students who view ability as expandable in response to experience and training are more likely to seek out challenging situations and learn from them. (p.131)

Researchers have found that negative dispositions towards mathematics increase as students move from elementary school to middle school to high school (Riling, 2018). In their analysis of data from a nationally administered survey and assessment of mathematics, Riling et al. (2018) found evidence of this decline in disposition: “In 2015, 47% of 8th graders indicated not liking math, up from 22% as 4th graders.” In addition, Riling et al. (2018) designed a survey for high school students about their disposition toward mathematics and found “students reported liking math class less in high school than in middle school” (para. 3). This trend indicates a steady decline in students’ dispositions toward mathematics as they move through middle school and high school. Importantly, the data results from the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) reveal that mathematics achievement and attitudes toward mathematics – consisting of students’ motivations like interest, utility value, and ability beliefs – have a bidirectional relationship; the more students identify positively toward mathematics, the greater their achievement and vice-versa (Mullis et al, 2012; Mullis et al., 2016; Mullis et al., 2020). Consequently, many secondary students develop negative dispositions toward mathematics during secondary school which hinders their progression in mathematics education and makes it less likely they will become successful, enthusiastic mathematics learners (Bobis, Anderson, Martin, & Way, 2011). Hence, it is time to emphasize and examine productive disposition as a means to understand students’ mathematical struggles and develop strategies to increase their mathematical success.

First, it is important to define what we mean by *disposition toward mathematics*. In a review of research about dispositions in mathematics education, Bobis, Anderson, Martin, and Way (2011) explains that disposition toward mathematics consists of affective and conative aspects:

- *affective* are the beliefs about oneself as a learner of mathematics, the nature of mathematics, the usefulness of mathematics, whether learning mathematics is worthwhile and sensible, and one's attitude toward mathematics;
- *conative* refers to one's effort, diligence, and persistence during mathematical activity.

We will look at both the negative and positive dispositions toward mathematics that determine whether and how a student will engage in mathematics learning activities. In regards to positive dispositions towards mathematics, we refer to this as a productive disposition; in their groundbreaking synthesis of research about the learning of mathematics, *Adding It Up: Helping Children Learn Mathematics*, Kilpatrick et. al. (2001) define a *productive disposition* as “the tendency to see sense in mathematics, to perceive it as both useful and worthwhile, to believe the steady effort in learning mathematics pays off, and to see oneself as an effective learner and doer of mathematics” (p. 131). Students’ dispositions toward mathematics are thus dependent on their affective perceptions and conative behaviors while engaged in mathematics learning.

Students who develop negative dispositions toward mathematics are more likely to develop an aversion to mathematics. For instance, mathematics anxiety is correlated with negative attitudes towards mathematics, and evidently, “17% of Americans suffer from high levels of mathematics anxiety” (Kennedy, 2019; Laney, 2019; Luttenberger, Wimmer, Paechter, 2018). Studies have revealed a correlation between mathematics anxiety and mathematics performance: as “attitudes towards mathematics tend to deteriorate with age during childhood and adolescence,” some of these students develop mathematics anxiety to the extent that they tend to “avoid activities and situations that involve mathematics” (Dowker, Sarkar, and Looi, 2016, p. 1).

The increasingly negative dispositions toward mathematics among adolescents – and the roots of these dispositions – is an issue of equity since students of color (Lubienski, S. T., 2002; Birenbaum & Nasser, F., 2006), low-income students (Marks, 2000), and students with disabilities (Kalambouka et al., 2016) report more negative dispositions toward mathematics and, as shared earlier, have less favorable outcomes in mathematics. However, students come to school with mostly positive dispositions toward mathematics (Carpenter et al., 1993; Zippert, 2019); the negative dispositions result from their experience with school mathematics and practices within mathematics classrooms — what we will call the roots of dispositions toward mathematics. This is what will be investigated.

Above all, it is evident that dispositions toward mathematics affect achievement in mathematics in a variety of ways. While there are many factors that contribute to the development of negative dispositions toward mathematics, for this inquiry three root causes will be examined as those most within a teacher’s control:

- 1) Learning Goals and Use of Assessments
- 2) Student Engagement and Classroom Climate
- 3) Mindset Toward Mathematics Ability

Analyzing these roots will help to then identify strategies that teachers can adopt to promote more productive dispositions. Each of these factors will be examined for its role in producing the negative dispositions toward mathematics found among so many young learners. Later, these same factors will be reframed in ways more likely to produce a productive disposition toward mathematics based on classroom research about more effective instructional practices.

The Roots of Negative Dispositions Toward Mathematics

Negative Root 1: Instrumental Learning Goals & Misuse of Assessment

Historically, throughout the 20th century and into the 21st, the educational goal in U. S. mathematics classrooms was the retention of rote facts and procedural knowledge, which led to learning through memorization and repetition as the primary pedagogy (Ellis & Berry, 2005; Mayer, 2002). This meant the learning goal for students was to memorize facts and mimic procedures. As a result, student learning was shallow and disconnected: “When teachers concentrate solely on rote learning, teaching and assessing focus solely on remembering elements or fragments of knowledge, often in isolation from any context” (Mayer, 2002, p.288). Mathematics was nothing more than a jumble of numbers, symbols, and rules that held little to no meaning or relevance for many students in such classrooms. Along with this emphasis on rote learning, assessments in mathematics have disproportionately focused on finding out how well students recall facts and carry out procedures to generate the right answers rather than on how well students understand mathematical ideas and apply mathematical reasoning (Ellis, 2008). Narrow learning goals and assessments negatively impact students’ dispositions toward mathematics, i.e., students will solely view mathematics as mindless procedures to be learned and, consequently, only have an instrumental understanding of mathematics (Skemp, 1978). Many of today's mathematics classrooms continue to reflect these same narrow learning goals and assessments, despite current standards which emphasize making sense of mathematics concepts and becoming proficient with problem-solving processes more so than the recall of rote knowledge and application of procedural skills (NCTM, 2000; 2014).

State-mandated assessments have a strong influence on classroom instruction and assessment. For instance, in a teacher survey, more than 80% indicated that the Virginia

Standards of Learning (SOL) test had impacted their instruction, particularly with regard to the content focus of daily lessons (Abrams, Pedulla, & Madaus, 2003). These large-scale standardized assessments are used to get a scope of how well schools and districts are doing in terms of education. As such, many educators feel pressure to ensure students do well in the standardized assessment despite the perception that these tests, as many educators have argued, “do not measure students’ ability or knowledge due to a discrepancy between what is being taught in class and what is asked on the tests,” and so, tests “are not aligned with the curriculum” (Moon, Brighton, Jarvas, & Hall, 2007. p. 87). Although pressure to improve education seems beneficial, educators tend to then over-emphasize improvement on standardized assessment scores which consequently undermines the effort to reform mathematics education, i.e., the principles described in the NCTM (2000) standards as explained by Ellis (2008). An overemphasis on standardized assessments often leads to a teacher-centered approach, which encourages learning through rote practice, a practice that fails to allow students to connect with the material and results in educators playing an authoritative role rather than a guiding role in their mathematics instruction (Bature, 2020).

In addition to negative impacts on instruction, an overreliance on standardized assessments outcomes often leads to labeling students as either being “good” at mathematics or being “bad” at mathematics and makes it all too easy to level students by placing them in either the “gifted” or “regular” classes, a practice that is increasingly understood as counterproductive in elementary school and middle school (NCTM, 2014). Thus, despite efforts to improve education through standardized testing, the “reliance on measures of statistical difference to produce ‘valid’ scores [on narrow measures of learning] assures...there must always be someone left behind” (Ellis, 2008, p.1348). As such, the way students identify themselves as mathematics

learners is in part based on what class they are placed in, their experiences with instruction in that class, and how well they do on exams that reflect the narrow set of knowledge found on standardized assessments – which historically have focused only on memorization and procedural knowledge.

In sum, when the learning goal is memorization and the use of procedures, educators tend to use teacher-centered instructional practices and test for shallow understanding (Mayer, 2002; Skemp, 1978). Skemp (1978) describes two types of student understanding resulting from the different approaches to instruction and assessment: relational understanding and instrumental understanding. *Relational understanding* means knowing a concept and being able to apply it flexibly to solve problems; relational learning leads to a deep, coherent, connected understanding of a subject. On the other hand, *instrumental understanding* is not true understanding but rather is the shallow, rote knowledge of facts and skills only useful for quick recall without concern for how this knowledge is connected or might apply to other tasks. Teaching mathematics in ways that promote instrumental understanding – without attention to coherence and sense-making – goes hand in hand with the roots of negative dispositions toward mathematics. Chubb (2016) has created a chart displaying the short-term and long-term effects of the matches made between how students are taught (instrumental versus relationally) and how they prefer to learn (instrumental versus relationally). In particular, the chart displays a negative outcome due to teaching for instrumental understanding no matter students' learning preference – instrumental or relational.

An example of this dynamic comes from a study by Lambert (2015) that focused on how two Latino/a students with learning disabilities were labeled as mathematics learners based on how they responded to different instructional strategies over the two semesters of a school year. Ms. Marquez, a Dominican-American secondary school teacher, taught the first-semester using

discussion-based pedagogy and the second semester using a mostly procedure-focused pedagogy. As noted by Lambert (2015), the learning approaches switched during the second semester because they focused “on memorizing procedures for a high-stakes test” (p.2). The two students, Ana and Luis, had different experiences over the two semesters: Ana had trouble in the first semester but did exceptionally well in the second semester; Luis was known as the “star conceptual student” during the first semester but had trouble in the second semester. Using Skemp’s (1978) terms, Ana learned best instrumentally and Luis learned best relationally, while the teachers taught the first semester relationally and the second semester instrumentally. Focusing on the second semester, when mathematics was taught instrumentally, there are clear impacts with respect to negative dispositions toward mathematics for each of the students. Luis resisted learning instrumentally; he continued to try to teach himself relationally. He experienced the immediate negative impacts of this as described in Chubb’s (2016) chart: the student who best learns relationally but is taught instrumentally “feels as though they are not smart enough to understand mathematics. Disengages, stops learning mathematics when given the opportunity.” Meanwhile, although Ana did well in the short-term, she will continue to think of mathematics as a discipline learned through narrow processes of memorization and mimicking procedures, which, in the long term, will limit her access to higher levels of study that require processes of mathematical reasoning and sense-making (Chubb, 2016; Ellis, 2008).

At the end of the school year, Ana’s and Luis’ teachers had to decide how to place these two different mathematics learners for the following school year and had been told that children were “to be placed in eighth-grade algebra based on ‘ability’” (Lambert, 2015, p.14). Because Ana was good at procedural learning, something reflected in the type of exams most used and valued by their teacher and school in the second semester, Ms. Marquez thought Ana should be

placed in the most advanced eighth-grade mathematics class. Ms. Marquez also considered “creating a class for Luis that stressed conceptual learning over rote memorization” despite the lack of emphasis in relational learning based on standardized assessments (Lambert, 2015; Moon, Brighton, Jarvas, & Hall, 2007). However, in the end Lambert (2015, p. 15) notes:

Ms. Alton [a special education teacher] disagreed with both suggestions. A conceptual class, she argued, would not give Luis what he “needs.” And, according to Ms. Alton, Ana should not be in the advanced class because she needed “additional support.”

Hence, both students were failed by narrowing mathematical learning and assessment to instrumental understanding. The learning goals and use of assessment in mathematics need to change to reflect more coherent relational understanding to allow teachers to support more meaningful learning for students like Luis and Ana.

Negative Root 2: Lack of Student Engagement & Negative Class Climate

Across many research papers (NCSSLE, 2021; Hu & Kuh, 2002; Marks, 2000; Reyes et al., 2012; Rumberger & Rotermund, 2012), student engagement has been identified as an essential component in educational success – i.e., it supports academic learning, student achievement, graduation rates, and personal development. And directly related to student engagement and overall student interactions is classroom climate – the characteristics of the learning environment that frame student engagement (Wang et. al., 2020). Within mathematics classrooms, student engagement (or lack thereof) is largely the result of the classroom climate created by the teacher.

As the National Center on Safe Supportive Learning Environments (NCSSLE) suggests, student engagement does not stand alone, for it is strongly associated with school climate; one

subcategory of school climate that I will focus on is classroom climate (Barksdale, Peters, Corrales, 2021). Student engagement and classroom climate are defined as follows:

- In terms of mathematics, student engagement refers to “students' involvement in mathematical learning activities,” that may spark collaboration, creativity, and connectivity, and “students’ commitment to learning the mathematical content” (Ingram, 2012, para.2).
- Classroom climate “refers to the prevailing mood, attitudes, standards, and tone that [teachers'] and [their] students feel when they are in [the] classroom” (Kamb, 2012, para. 1); there are two types of classroom climate that may occur: “A negative classroom climate can feel hostile, chaotic, and out of control [while a] positive classroom climate feels safe, respectful, welcoming, and supportive of student learning” (Kamb, para.1).

In their study of varying levels of disengagement and engagement among urban adolescents, Fredricks, Parr, Wang, and Braur (2019) describe how students were classified as highly engaged, unevenly engaged, or disengaged depending on three factors: (i) students’ relationships with teachers, (ii) peer relationships, and (iii) classroom structure. The researchers found that many students in the middle schools and high schools they studied felt alienated and became less engaged over time – and thus identified as unevenly engaged or disengaged – when the following occurred:

- (i) ***Inability to Form Teacher-Student Relationships*** Research has found that teacher-student relationships “in mathematics classes deteriorated after the transition from the primary to secondary school” which negatively affected students’ dispositions toward mathematics (Deieso, 2016, p. 3; Prewett, Bergin, & Huang, 2019). Secondary

school students who did not connect with their teachers on a positive level felt that “these teachers did not trust or respect them, judged them unfairly, and made assumptions about their achievement and behavior based on other students’ behavior in school” (Fredricks et al., 2019, pp. 502 - 503). Specifically, negative teacher-student relationships occur when teachers too narrowly focus on rote learning and grades rather than on student engagement in learning, as demonstrated in Daniels and Arapostathis’ (2005) study which examines why students may choose to disengage. Negative teacher-student relationships are counterproductive (Mistele and Louis, 2011); these relationships typically lead to poor classroom management and control, low student attainment levels, and eventual disrespect from the same students” (Pilgrim, para.3).

(ii) *Inability to Form Connections Among Peers* In a negative classroom environment and when the learning goals are narrowly focused on memorization and attaining correct answers – typically demonstrated through teacher-centered instruction – competitive and individualistic goal structures are prompted and lead to negative interdependence and no interdependence, respectively (Roseth et al., 2008). As defined by Roseth et al. (2008), *negative interdependence* “exists when individuals perceive that they can obtain their goals if and only if the other individuals with whom they are competitively linked fail to obtain their goals” and *no interdependence* “exists when individuals perceive that they can reach their goal regardless of whether other individuals attain or do not attain their goals” (p. 225). In other words, students' negative interdependence and lack of interdependence occur when students work individually and competitively toward an academic goal of memorizing mathematics content and getting correct answers to procedural problems, both features of teacher-centered mathematics lessons (Turner et al,

2002), which contributes to a negative classroom peer climate. *Classroom peer climate* reflects “the quality of collective interpersonal relationships among students” (Shim, Kiefer, & Wang, 2013, p. 292); hence, we define *negative classroom peer climate* as consisting of the negative interdependence and no interdependence that results in a lack of interaction, collaboration, and sense of belonging. Notably, Roseth et al. (2008) found that “for early adolescents, cooperative goal structures were associated with higher levels of achievement than were competitive or individualistic goal structures” (p. 237) when comparing the levels of achievement associated with cooperative goal structures versus individualistic goal structures. In mathematics especially, avoidance of seeking help occurs, in part, because of the negative peer climate (Shim, Kiefer, & Wang, 2013; Turner et al, 2002).

(iii) *Negative Classroom Structure* In the middle school and high school mathematics classes studied by Fredricks et. al. (2019), students commented that not understanding the content was part of the reason for feeling unevenly engaged or completely disengaged: “... not knowing the answer and feeling confused ...led to frustration and a likelihood of giving up” (Fredricks et. al., 2019, p.506). The students’ feelings of incompetence towards their mathematical knowledge was generated from the negative class climate built from mathematics activities that limited opportunities for sense making and narrowed definitions of mathematics ability (a topic that will be explored the last negative root section that follows). For instance, when classwork is passive or lacks critical thinking - a result of the narrow learning goals and assessments practiced in a class using teacher-centered pedagogy - this “does not align with students’ needs, and

capacity for cognitively complex and demanding tasks, [and] students are more likely to disengage from learning” (Wang, Hofkens, and Ye, 2020, p.1988).

These three causes of unevenly engaged or disengaged students align with Louie’s (2017) exclusionary frame regarding the nature of (a) mathematics activity and (b) mathematics ability. In her examination of student experiences in so-called inclusive and exclusionary mathematics classrooms, Louie (2017) found five types of framing of mathematical activity and ability: (1) the rote practice frame, (2) the hierarchical ability frame, (3) the sense-making frame, (4) the multidimensional mathematics frame, and (5) the multidimensional ability frame (p.496). Frames (1) and (2) reflect an exclusionary culture that views mathematics as “a collection of discrete skills and students as recipients” which contributes to students' negative dispositions toward mathematics. Despite the four teachers studied “express[ing] a commitment to empowering students who had not been well-served by their previous mathematics learning experiences,” (Louie, p.512) and feeling that they were using equitable and inclusive practices, the activities and framework of mathematics classroom - the class climate - actually reflected an exclusionary frame. Louie offers possible interpretations of the persistence of exclusionary framing: i.e., teachers’ backgrounds and beliefs about mathematics and the dominant culture of mathematics education (pp.513-514). Essentially, negative dispositions toward mathematics are worsened through the continuing practice of teacher-centered instruction, rote learning and a negative class climate.

Hogan’s (2008) case study of a Yup'ik middle schooler, Nora, provides a stark example of the impact of class climate on student engagement. Nora was described as a "genius in math" by her sixth-grade teacher Diana; however, Nora was described as a "D+ student" by her seventh-grade teacher Michael (Hogan, 2008). From sixth to seventh grade, Nora shifts from

being a leader and working in groups to working silently and independently. What changed from one school year to the next? Specifically, her sixth and seventh-grade teachers produced different class climates based on the (a) mathematics activity frame resulting from the type of pedagogy used and (b) definition of mathematics ability, affecting level of student engagement, such that Nora learned and practiced mathematics differently from one year to the next: "Neither Diana nor Michael was wrong in their assessment of Nora as a math learner, given the designs, discourses, practices, and expectations of their respective classrooms" (Hogan, p.109). It was Nora's seventh-grade year when the class climate limited positive student engagement: Nora's seventh-grade teacher Michael used exclusionary strategies. Since Michael's main focus was on raising student scores on the state standardized assessment, Michael taught his classes by starting with a mini-lecture and providing procedural examples. Candy was given to anyone who caught a classmate with a mistake. Then, Micheal assigned classwork that reflected practicing the procedure he had provided; the classwork was assigned as individual work with the option of working in groups. Lastly, if students finished their classwork early, they would get free time on the computers that were lined up by the classroom walls. This classroom structure created a competitive, individualistic space for students, creating a class with a lack of student engagement, especially since many students aimed to finish the procedural types of mathematics activities to have free time on the computers. In sum, the negative class climate resulted from (a) the emphasis on rote instrumental learning using uncreative mathematics activities and (b) the low level of student engagement based on how mathematics ability was determined by speed and correctness.

Overall, the lack of engagement based on the conditions described by [Fredricks et. al., 2019](#) and seen in [Hogan's \(2008\)](#) case study align with findings of studies of student engagement

in regard to mathematics; in classes with low levels of engagement in which students feel alienated and distant from mathematics, students further develop negative dispositions toward mathematics that harm the way they feel about themselves, the subject of mathematics, and even school overall (Fredricks et. al., 2016).

Negative Root 3: Fixed Mindset about Ability

One's mindset affects both effort and outcomes in a range of activities from academics to sports to relationships to work. Mindset is “the established set of attitudes and beliefs held by someone” about their ability (Clyatt, 2017, p.1). Dweck (2006) discusses how the two basic mindsets, the fixed and growth mindset, relate to how people respond to life’s challenges based on their views of failures, abilities, relationships, and the like. Not surprisingly, "one's mindset toward intelligence serves as a predictor of one's success in mathematics" (Willingham et al., 2021). If a student believes they cannot “do mathematics” or that being smart in mathematics is an unchangeable trait that only some are lucky to have, they are more likely to give up before trying or getting through a challenge. But, if students believe in their effort and ability to be successful despite the challenges they may face, they are more likely to persevere and succeed. Students will believe in their mathematics ability when they believe in themselves and when their teachers and parents show their belief in these students' abilities (Dweck, 2008). For instance, Dweck (2008) shares one of her Columbia University student’s reflections on his history class:

I remember often being praised for my intelligence rather than my efforts, and slowly but surely I developed an aversion to difficult challenges. Most surprisingly, this extended beyond academic and even athletic challenges to emotional challenges. This was my

greatest learning disability—this tendency to see performance as a reflection of character and, if I could not accomplish something right away, to avoid that task or treat it with contempt. (p.97)

When it comes to the learning of mathematics, it is critical to support the shift of students' negative fixed mindsets to positive growth mindsets. By looking at students' mindsets, we can better understand the negative dispositions toward mathematics.

By definition, a *fixed mindset* is present when “individuals adopt performance goals and exhibit helpless, maladaptive responses to challenges to that ability” (Willingham et al., 2021, p.235); in other words, learners with a fixed mindset tend to believe that they have particular predetermined abilities defined by their mistakes. Consequently, these students stray away from attempting challenging problems; they tend to believe that if they do not try, they will not fail. On the other hand, a *growth mindset* about one's ability leads learners to “exhibit adaptive responses to challenges to that ability” (Willingham et al., 2021, p.235); in other words, learners with a growth mindset tend to embrace challenges and mistakes as important parts of the learning process and perceive ability as malleable, that through effort one can improve.

It is specifically the fixed mindset that plays a part in students' negative dispositions toward mathematics. Mathematics students with a fixed mindset do not believe in their improvement after misunderstanding a mathematics problem and perceive ability as an unalterable trait, that one is either good at mathematics or not (Willingham et al., 2021). One group of mathematics teachers aiming to enhance mathematics education refers to themselves as the [Mathematical Agency Improvement Community \(MAIC\)](#). The MAIC seeks to abolish the phrase “I'm not a math person” by introducing student-centered practices of learning mathematics through reasoning and sense-making along with peer collaboration. On their

website, the [MAIC](#) shares videos of interviews with students before and after experiencing a student-centered classroom. In the video of eighth-grade students sharing their prior experiences in a classrooms that promoted a fixed mindset, they emphasized how it was not enjoyable; it felt like a competition; it felt uncomfortable because “people were going to judge you a certain way” ([MAIC, Status & Mindset Interventions video, n.d.](#)). One student even remarked, “I needed to know my answer instead of explaining my answer” ([Status & Mindset Interventions](#)). Hence, students that experienced a fixed mindset approach felt that mathematics was either right or wrong, individualistic and competitive, and that mathematics was only for specific people. This fixed mindset approach, which may not necessarily be intentional on the part of the teacher, creates negative dispositions toward mathematics and is often reflected in educators' use of language. [Waller and Marzocchi \(2020\)](#) emphasize the need for teachers to shift away from fixed mindset language and toward growth mindset language, i.e. language that inspires, in order to position students within the mathematics community. Some examples of negative fixed mindset language shared by [Waller and Marzocchi's \(2020, p.547-548\)](#) include:

- Teacher’s Preferred Method: “How I like to do it...,”
 - By showing a dominant procedure of doing a mathematics problem, students only focus on replicating the solution and do not believe other strategies they might have are appropriate or valued.
- “Clearly”/ “ obviously”/”it’s easy”/ “of course”/etc.
 - Some students are still processing past concepts or have learning gaps; consequently, many students will feel incompetent in their mathematics ability.
- Labeling students such as “high” or “low”

- The education system reinforces the fixed mindset through practices of labeling and tracking students, especially in mathematics. As [Kitchen et al. \(2017\)](#) reveal, labeling in mathematics education is a result of the misuse of assessment scores and the failure to question stereotypes of who – among students of different socioeconomic backgrounds – are considered mathematics people. This not only harms the instruction used in a classroom but also negatively affects students’ mathematical identity. In the U.S., mathematics is the most tracked subject, and typically, this tracking “begins in the early years of elementary school or the beginning of middle school in fifth or sixth grade” ([Kitchen, p.7](#)). Although some may have thought labeling and tracking would help in distributing the resources students required, it does the exact opposite in most cases.

In summary, a fixed mindset is reinforced, perhaps unintentionally, in teacher-centered approaches to mathematics education, worsening students’ negative dispositions toward mathematics and leading to avoidance of challenges, cheating, and other unproductive habits.

Combating the Negative Roots Toward Equitable Outcomes

[NCTM \(2000, p.12\)](#) describes equity as follows:

All students, regardless of their personal characteristics, backgrounds, or physical challenges, must have opportunities to study—and support to learn—mathematics. Equity does not mean that every student should receive identical instruction; instead, it demands that reasonable and appropriate accommodations be made as needed to promote access and attainment for all students.

In other words, equity means providing the necessary support and resources catering to each student's needs no matter their personal identities. With respect to mathematics, equity occurs when “all students have access to a high quality mathematics curriculum, effective teaching and learning, high expectations, and the support and resources needed to maximize their learning potential” (NCTM, 2014, p.59). 2Partner, a mathematics education consulting group, uses Gutierrez's (2009, 2012) work to define four dimensions of equity in mathematics learning: access, power, identity, and achievement. *Access* relates to the mathematical resources made available to the student; *power* is the measure of student opportunities to have a voice in the classroom and contribute to the mathematical ideas being developed; *identity* refers to how students view themselves as mathematical thinkers and the relatedness of mathematics to their lives; and *achievement* is the measurable student outcomes. Each of these dimensions has a connection to students' dispositions toward mathematics (Gresalfi, 2009,2006; Grasalfi & Cobb, 2006). Notably, all four of the dimensions of equity in mathematics learning are important for a productive classroom: as Gutierrez (2012) notes, the focus on a single dimension such as achievement is “a necessary but insufficient approach to equity” (p.19). The education community needs to start focusing on helping people (i.e., educators, parents, and, especially, students) develop productive dispositions toward mathematics by attending to all four dimensions of equity. And so, it is critical to change the conditions that are at the root of students' negative dispositions toward mathematics. As Ellis and Berry (2005) describe, the past ways of thinking about mathematics education have affected the way it is predominantly taught today, through drill and procedural practice:

Despite a century of “reform” efforts school mathematics practices in the late twentieth century...research in mathematics classrooms during the latter years of the

twentieth century found that in the United States teachers were still the center of authority, disseminating rote skills and procedural knowledge to their students who then worked individually on sets of problems in order to internalize this knowledge.

(p.10)

Learning mathematics through teacher-centered rote factual recall and procedural practice restricts students to a narrow view of mathematics based on memorization and mimicry without reasoning and sense-making; this method does not allow students to develop an understanding of mathematical concepts and relationships or to become critical mathematical thinkers.

By using teaching methods based on outdated perspectives toward mathematics, we ignore the advancements and changes occurring almost every day driven by computers making millions of mathematical calculations every second based on unimaginable amounts of data garnered from all manner of daily activities. Mathematics needs to be taught in such a way that helps students gain the necessary skills for their future adult life. As [Trilling \(2009\)](#) explains,

We face demands from the new global knowledge economy; from the converging forces of knowledge work, digital tools, and lifestyles; from modern learning research; and from the need for the skills most in demand in our times: problem-solving, being creative and innovative, communicating, collaborating, being flexible, and so on ([pp.38-39](#)).

Looking back at how mathematics has been taught over the years, the goals do not meet what [Trilling \(2009\)](#) emphasizes as the necessary fundamental skills students need in this day and age.

The three roots described in “The Roots of Negative Dispositions Towards Mathematics” section reveal the restrictions placed on students’ true mathematical capabilities. Hence, we must come to understand the contrast between two particular instructional approaches: teacher-centered and student-centered. We need to create a system that allows us to shift from

classroom characteristics in the teacher-centered approach – rooted in narrow perspectives about mathematics and about students’ abilities – to the classroom characteristics in the student-centered approach – grounded in a richer vision of mathematics as a way of quantitative sense-making and students as capable of developing understandings of mathematics that specifically nurtures productive dispositions toward the subject. As depicted in Table 1, the teacher-centered approach and student-centered approach can be characterized by different (a) learning goals, (b) types of learning, (c) types of understanding, (d) instructional strategies, and (e) mindsets. The teacher-centered characteristics were reflected in “The Roots of Negative Dispositions Towards Mathematics.” Now, I will explore how the student-centered approach represents a shift toward nurturing more positive dispositions. I will also examine the impact on equity in mathematics education outcomes that may result from this shift through the lens of Gutierrez’s (2009, 2012) four dimensions of equity.

Positive Root 1: Relational Learning Goals & Advantageous Use of Assessment

As displayed earlier in “Instrumental Learning Goals & Misuse of Assessment,” memorization and mimicry as the learning goal lead educators to teach and test for instrumental understanding which contributes to students’ negative dispositions toward mathematics. Accordingly, learning goals need to shift to an emphasis on reasoning, sense-making, and the transfer of mathematical knowledge and assessment must focus more on relational understanding and the use of assessment to inform further learning.

Educational psychologist Richard Mayer’s (2002) analysis offers a contrasting view of rote learning versus meaningful learning, which correspond with the teacher-centered and student-centered approaches (see Table 1, parts a and b). For meaningful learning to occur,

Mayer explains that “remembering knowledge is integrated within the larger task of constructing new knowledge or solving new problems” (p.228). Meaningful learning recognizes the importance of rote learning to an extent but emphasizes the need to be able to grasp the concept and context of mathematical ideas. Further, by emphasizing the cognitive processes found in meaningful learning, Mayer (2002) seeks to "help educators (including test designers) broaden the way they assess learning" (p. 232). Specifically, this means assessing for transfer (an important part of relational learning) versus simple retention (also known as memorization). Table 2 lists the many complex cognitive processes that go into meaningful learning, making clear the depth that accompanies meaningful learning.

In particular, when a teacher plans for meaningful learning and assesses for relational understanding, students are more likely to develop a positive disposition toward mathematics. Consider, again, Chubb’s (2016) chart citing Skemp (1978): the short and long-term effects of teachers teaching for relational understanding—for students who prefer to learn instrumentally as well as those who prefer to learn relationally—prove to be beneficial. For instance, Luis (the student from Lambert’s (2015) case study) had the best results when Ms. Marquez taught relationally in the first semester and commented: “I like challenging more stuff, and the more challenging, it is like a problem, the more challenging, the more problems in your head, so it makes you think about it more” (p. 13).

Meaningful learning requires teaching for relational understanding. Such lessons include mathematics questions that are framed to spark curiosity and creativity, making learning more coherent and more interesting. Chubb (2022) cites mathematics educator Marian Small’s question types - Type 1 and Type 2 - as one framework for distinguishing between rote and meaningful learning. *Type 1 problems* are questions asked in order to receive a specific value as

an answer. Meanwhile, *Type 2 problems* are questions that may be answered with a variety of possible open-ended responses and strategies such that students are meant to think about what they have been asked, to make connections, and to make sense. Notably, Type 1 problems are given by teachers who teach for instrumental understanding while Type 2 problems are more often given by teachers who teach for relational understanding. Hence, a lesson taught for relational understanding may include a warm up (Type 2) question or activity that gives an opportunity for students to develop some mathematical ideas that build from or connect to prior knowledge; this can then be followed by activities for which the teacher will gradually introduce more formal mathematical terms and notation. Rather than being told how to use a predetermined procedure for which they have no basis for understanding, a relational learning lesson gives students a chance to try a mathematics problem and develop their own strategies which a teacher then helps to refine and revise.

In addition to shifts in lesson design, in response to standards such as Common Core that emphasize transferring or connecting mathematical conceptual knowledge as the learning goal, there have also been efforts to make standardized assessments more inclusive of conceptual knowledge. For example, the [California Assessment of Student Performance and Progress' \(CAASPP\) Smarter Balanced Summative Assessment](#) includes items that get at students' understanding of mathematical relationships and provides scores reports that are more helpful than a simple scale score by offering feedback on students' strengths and areas for improvement. While far from perfect, this represents a step in a positive direction. Since, as was discussed earlier, it is known that assessments influence instruction, standardized assessments that include items designed to get at conceptual, relational understanding will be more likely to positively influence the ways teachers teach and assess their students ([Ellis, 2008](#)).

An important change in classroom assessment that better supports relational learning is to make more frequent use of formative assessment. *Formative assessment* is defined as an assessment designed “to monitor student progress during the learning process” (Dunn & Mulvenon, 2009, pp.2-3). In particular, student-centered learning promotes the use of formative assessments that gives teachers and students specific feedback meant to further learning rather than finite scores used for labeling and sorting students. Rather than being only evaluative, formative assessments help students to get a gauge of their mathematics strengths and identify areas in which they need to grow.

Equitable Mathematics Outcomes (Access & Achievement). The CCSSM only provides content standards - what educators need to teach students - not how these standards should be taught. Memorizing procedures will not help in the long run; the negative root reflected in teacher-centered learning (consisting of learning for memorization through rote learning and testing for instrumental understanding) is unproductive and produces negative dispositions toward mathematics, which does not lead to more equitable outcomes. Shifting to the positive root reflected in student-centered learning (consisting of preparing students to transfer mathematics knowledge through meaningful learning and assessing formatively for relational understanding) promotes more equitable mathematics outcomes. Specifically, meaningful learning gives rise to the availability of equitable access to content through activities encouraging relational understanding, i.e. Small’s Type 2 questions give students a chance to make sense of and relate to mathematics concepts. Gutierrez’s (2009, 2012) access dimension is addressed since students are given the opportunity to learn from Type 2 questions, or any other activities that allow students to think and reason mathematically. However, access alone is not enough. And so, as a result of the access dimension being addressed, student achievement must

also be a focus using formative assessments. From activities that include Type 2 questions, formative assessments will be used to check for relational understanding and provide feedback on students' mathematics strengths and capabilities as well as their areas for improvement. The use of formative assessments goes beyond simply measuring student outcomes; educators use formative assessment data to acknowledge and focus on the need to provide the appropriate support and accommodations for students to be successful. Thus, this positive root promotes productive dispositions from which the achievement dimension follows. These productive dispositions result in equitable mathematics outcomes as follows:

- Students focus on the process of mathematical reasoning;
- Assessments are used as tools for gaining feedback about learning;
- Educators make the standards much more meaningful.

Overall, when Gutierrez's (2009, 2012) access and achievement dimensions have been addressed, teachers will be better able to provide the tools each of their students need to be able to successfully learn mathematics. These students will then be able to become critical mathematics thinkers and be prepared to achieve in higher level mathematics courses.

Positive Root 2: Increasing Student Engagement & Setting a Positive Class Climate

“Lack of Student Engagement & Negative Class Climate” characterizes student disengagement resulting from exclusionary practices that form a negative classroom climate; this encourages negative dispositions toward mathematics. To combat this negative root, it is important to create a more inclusive class climate which increases student engagement. And so, we now look at – as [Nguyen and Miller \(2018\)](#) have noted – the positive association of increasing student engagement with setting a positive classroom climate.

As mentioned previously, [Fredericks et al. \(2019\)](#) discussed the causes for middle school and high school students identifying as unevenly engaged or disengaged and the causes for them identifying as highly engaged. In particular, adolescent students felt highly engaged when the following occurred:

(i) *Healthy Teacher-Student Relationships* Teachers created a positive classroom climate by providing encouragement and support, having high expectations, adjusting tasks accordingly, moving students around to make sure peers are not being disruptive, and being strict but caring ([Fredericks, et al., 2019](#); [Kamb, 2012](#); [Klem, 2004](#)). The positive classroom climate allowed teachers to develop positive relationships with students, and these teachers were often described as “friendly and welcoming, a source of academic and emotional support, and as advocates for them when [students] are having difficulty” ([Fredericks, et al., 2019, p.501](#)). A straightforward way of increasing student engagement through class climate is by having educators greet their students ([Allday & Pakurar, 2007](#); [Cook et al. 2018](#)). Evidently, by having mathematics (and English) teachers welcome their students into their classrooms, student engagement increased by 20% ([Cook et al., 2018, p.156](#)). In sum, teachers do not have to go as far as to become students’ friends; rather, simple polite gestures, demonstration of caring and respect, and setting up boundaries will help increase healthy, positive teacher-student relationships. As a result, students are more motivated to engage and to report feelings of belonging which leads to students’ performing well academically ([Fredriksen & Rhodes, 2004](#); [Umarji, Dicke, Safavin, Karebenick, & Eccles, 2021](#)).

(ii) *Peer Support* Students report higher levels of engagement when their peers are supportive academically and emotionally such that the classroom climate allows students

to feel “accepted, welcomed, and respected by their peers at school” (Fredericks et al., 2019, p.504). As a result of being in a mathematics class with a positive classroom climate, students can positively interact with one another – i.e., compare experiences, share ideas, articulate mathematical thinking, pose questions, gain confidence, and test each other for true understanding (Chapman, 2004). In this positive classroom climate, collaborative goal structures are promoted and establish *positive interdependence*, “when individuals perceive that they can reach their goals if and only if the other individuals with whom they are cooperatively linked also reach their goals” (Roseth et al., 2008, p.225). The student-centered approach to learning mathematics is closely aligned with these principles.

(iii) Positive Classroom Structure When teachers give words of encouragement and positive feedback on their academic abilities, students report feeling capable and competent in their class. As a result, these students tend to have higher levels of engagement. In the positive classroom climate, teachers “must serve in the role as the facilitator and allow students to persevere through the process of finding a technique for solving new problems (Walker, 2015, p.15). To serve as a facilitator, mathematics teachers must provide purposeful activities (Chapman, 2004; Fredriksen & Rhodes, 2004). These purposeful mathematics activities are facilitated best by how teachers frame questions and give students time to think mathematically (Shahrill, 2013).

These three classroom climate characteristics that promote highly engaged students align well with Louie’s (2017) inclusionary frames regarding the nature of mathematics activity and ability. Frames (3) to (5), mentioned previously, are part of an inclusive culture that views students as “producers of knowledge” (Louie, 2017, p.513). To be specific, inclusive strategies

regarding mathematics learning include implementing mathematics tasks that “require them [students] to reason mathematically” and allow students to be “engaged in a productive struggle” (Walker, p.15). We can further examine this idea through a case study.

When teachers create a learning environment allowing creativity, collaboration, and connection to occur alongside providing plenty of resources and support, students are more likely to attain higher mathematics achievement levels (Barksdale, Peters, & Corrales, 2021; NCTM, 2014). In Hogan’s (2008) case study, Nora’s sixth-grade teacher Diana used inclusive strategies that encouraged a positive classroom climate and, therefore, a productive disposition. In particular, Diana used a culturally relevant teaching approach – relating one’s culture to mathematical concepts. This approach is seen best in Hogan’s description of the Fish Rack Module: the Yup’ik elders (from the community in which the school was located) use body measurements to build fish racks relative to the user’s size correctly, so Diana related Yup’ik terms for body measurements to the mathematical concept of proportions that her students were learning. Consequently, Diana created an inclusive class with high engagement: as Yup’ik students, Nora and her sixth-grade peers worked collaboratively on a culturally relevant mathematics activity and focused on finding ways to arrive at a solution that made sense to them both mathematically and culturally. In all, the positive class climate resulted from (a) the emphasis on building connections, experimenting, and sense-making and (b) the high level of student engagement based on how the various mathematics capabilities of each person were utilized as a strength.

Equitable Mathematics Outcomes (Power & Achievement). Altogether, a positive class climate is critical to adolescents’ mathematics engagement and achievement (Wang et al., 2020). Based on the conditions described by Fredricks et al., 2019 and seen in Hogan’s (2008) case

study, high engagement leads to more equitable mathematics outcomes. The type of teaching strategy in a mathematics classroom that gives students' power, or a voice, heavily influences the level of equity. In particular, increasing student engagement and ensuring a positive classroom climate follows from Gutierrez's (2009, 2012) power dimension through adopting inclusive pedagogy, all of which results in

- Forming healthy, effective teacher-students relationships;
- Creating a class setting allowing student collaboration for which students feel a sense of belonging;
- Setting high expectations for students;
- Validating students' cultures and experience by relating mathematics content to students through contextual, cultural, and relational learning
- Creating critical thinkers; and
- Using students' varying mathematics strengths.

Students will become mathematical thinkers and have the courage to share their mathematical ideas with their peers and teachers. Subsequently, Gutierrez's (2009, 2012) achievement dimension is advanced when students develop productive dispositions needed to create an equitable mathematics classroom.

Positive Root 3: Supporting the Growth Mindset

In "Fixed Mindset about Ability," a fixed mindset creates or amplifies negative dispositions toward mathematics by making students who struggle believe that no matter their effort, they cannot be successful in mathematics. We combat this by fostering a growth mindset in mathematics classrooms. As defined earlier, students with a growth mindset embrace mistakes

and believe they will improve through perseverance; they are willing to fail and learn from mistakes and missteps. To emphasize a growth mindset, educators need to include more positive language or, as [Waller and Marzocchi \(2020\)](#) phrase it, “language that inspires.”

Some examples of positive language from [Waller and Marzocchi](#) that specifically combats a fixed mindset and promotes a growth mindset include:

- Centering student thinking rather than teacher or textbook solution strategies: “Let’s take a look at this solution and see if we can make sense of it.”
 - Rather than focusing on one procedural approach from the teacher or textbook, students will focus on different solution strategies and learn that their approaches to the problem do not need to look the same. The focus is on mathematical reasoning and sense-making.
- “Hmmm, this looks familiar ... turn to your partner and see if you can remember the result of ...”
 - This allows students to work with one another and have a fruitful discussion about a mathematics problem.
 - The way a question is framed matters! [Small \(2012\)](#) shares, “the use of these straightforward but powerful differentiation strategies will lead to a classroom with much higher engagement levels, much less frustration, and much more math learning, thinking, and talking—leveling a much more positive attitude [which is part of productive disposition] towards math for students” (p.202). Hence, framing questions to be more open and inquisitive of students’ ideas leads to a growth mindset.

- “We are learning so much from the variety of solutions around the room. We should be proud of our hard work to explain our own thinking and understand the thinking of others. We learn better together.”
 - Educators need first to acknowledge that every student is capable, and hence, educators should have high expectations for every student. As [Waller and Marzoochi](#) put it, educators need to explicitly expand the definition of who is “good” at mathematics and base it on each student’s efforts to “build new mathematical knowledge from current mathematical knowledge” (p. 549).

Consider the video interviews with students in classrooms of teachers in the [MAIC](#): in the more inclusive classrooms – in which the teacher includes talking about growth mindset and uses a student-centered approach – the students’ feelings about mathematics shifted away from negative dispositions toward a more positive view of their ability to learn mathematics. One student remarked that “debates focused on which idea makes sense versus which idea is right or wrong,” signaling an intentional effort of their teacher to emphasize relational understanding and value students’ contributions. Another female eighth-grade student in a MAIC classroom explained:

People think math since it's hard, that it's terrible and not fun to do, but in actuality, it's fun. Yes, it's maybe hard, but that's kind of the fun behind it. The harder it gets, the more you think, and the more you think, the more your brain grows. And the more mistakes you make, literally, synapses in your brain connect, and you get, your brain grows ([Status & Mindset Interventions](#)).

This student was onto something. [Boaler \(2016\)](#) explained that brain growth – defined by increased neural connectivity – occurs when people make mistakes. Evidently, “people with a

growth mindset have greater brain activity when they make mistakes” (Moser et al. in Boaler, 2016, p.2). After experiencing a growth mindset approach, the eighth-grade students in MAIC classrooms began to develop more productive dispositions, i.e. that mathematics is about reasoning, being creative, and making mistakes, all of which lead to students embracing mistakes and developing positive mathematics identities.

Equitable Mathematics Outcomes (Identity & Achievement). Implementing the growth mindset in secondary school mathematics classrooms will encourage productive dispositions for which more equitable mathematics outcomes follow. Students will view themselves as mathematical thinkers because they are able to see that mistakes do not define them as a math person or not; rather, mistakes (and struggle) are an expected and productive part of learning. The development of these positive mathematics identities – reflected in the language recommended by Waller and Marzoochi (2020) and heard in the student interviews done by the MAIC – will, in part, increase student achievement and overall solidify productive dispositions. Most of all, Gutierrez’s (2009, 2012) identity dimension is advanced. In sum, the following equitable outcomes will be more likely to occur:

- Students further develop positive mathematics identities;
- Educators and students embrace mistakes as expected and productive;
- Students believe that mathematics is for everyone and that there is no such thing as a mathematics person;
- Students grow to enjoy mathematics including their struggles.

Altogether, these equitable outcomes aid in meeting Gutierrez’s (2009, 2012) achievement dimension.

Conclusion

Having examined many different research papers and case studies, it is evident that more productive dispositions toward mathematics can be promoted and will contribute to more equitable classrooms when the following conditions exist: (1) The learning goal is to form connections and to make sense rather than to merely memorize information and mimic procedures; (2) The classroom reflects an inclusionary climate that encourages student engagement versus an exclusionary climate that does not provide students the chance to collaborate or connect with the mathematics material or with one another; and (3) Teachers communicate and nurture a growth mindset toward mathematics for all students (i.e., it is okay to make mistakes because we can learn from them) versus reinforcing a narrow fixed mindset in which only a few students are deemed capable of succeeding with mathematics.

Making these shifts away from the negative roots within teacher-centered learning and toward the positive roots in student-centered learning will not happen overnight. Rather, each positive root must be planted and nurtured gradually. For instance, one can start their student-centered learning journey by implementing the practice of promoting a growth mindset, taking time to define growth mindset to the students, emphasizing that mistakes are good, and using positive language.

As I examined only three roots of negative dispositions toward mathematics - those most within a teacher's control - I did not explore additional roots of negative dispositions toward mathematics that are also important to keep in mind, i.e. the effects of parental involvement when parents have a negative disposition from their experiences with mathematics ([Perry & Docket, 2008](#)). Nonetheless, I am able to conclude that the negative dispositions toward

mathematics found among many adolescent learners at least in part come from specific classroom factors over which teachers have influence. Using the strategies associated with a student-centered approach to mathematics learning allows students the space to reclaim what these negative mathematical dispositions have taken away from them - a positive mathematical identity and greater success with mathematics.

The shift forward to a more student-centered approach that produces a productive disposition toward mathematics allows future and current educators to reflect upon what they can do in their practice. In my case, as I prepare to enter the teaching profession, I must keep in mind the importance of developing a productive disposition toward mathematics among my students, particularly those from marginalized backgrounds. The bulleted summary that follows will help me to stay focused on this goal throughout my credential coursework, fieldwork, and into my early career:

- ❖ **Plan lessons and assess learning in a way that helps students to connect and transfer their knowledge.** Rather than viewing assessments as the reason to teach with procedural learning, think about relational learning goals and how to design lessons that emphasize connections within mathematics and beyond mathematics to the worlds of students' lives. Use assessment to inform instruction (how well are my lessons working?) and to guide students' further learning (what are their strengths and areas for improvement?).
 - Create/find and use activities related to students and the real world.
 - Be careful not to label/track students so that you are not biased towards your students.
- ❖ **Provide a safe space that encourages student engagement.** I will seek to create a positive classroom climate and focus on supporting students in making sense of

mathematics through collaboration and communication in order to increase student engagement.

- Challenge students with more open-ended questions that allow them to think mathematically.
- Give students space that supports creativity, collaboration, and connectivity through teaching approaches like culturally responsive practices, active learning, etc.
- Interact and effectively communicate with students and create an environment revolving around the need for respect for both teacher and students.
- Be sensitive to diversity and students' identities.

❖ **Teach about and model a growth mindset.** By encouraging mistakes and revisions in the classroom, student mathematical dispositions will shift from negative to positive.

- Be careful with language and praise. Praise students for improvement, effort, behavior, and academic progress, not just for getting the correct answer.
- Have high expectations for students.

Communicating a belief that mathematics is purposeful and valuable and that everyone can be a mathematics person will help students, as well as teachers and parents, develop into brilliant mathematical thinkers. When educators acknowledge the negative roots present in many mathematics classrooms today and consider strategies that sow and nurture more positive roots, they will be more likely to enhance productive dispositions toward mathematics. I look forward to contributing to this transformation.

Appendix

Table 1

Classroom Factors in a Teacher-Centered Approach versus Student-Centered Approach

Classroom Factors	Teacher-Centered Approach	Student-Centered Approach
(a) Learning Goal	Memorization	Transfer
(b) Type of Learning	Rote	Meaningful
(c) Type of Understanding	Instrumental	Relational
(d) Type of Strategy	Exclusive	Inclusive
(e) Type of Mindset	Fixed	Growth

Learning Goals and Types of Learning cited from [Mayer \(2002\)](#).

Types of Understanding cited from [Skemp \(1978\)](#).

Types of Mindset cited from [MAIC](#).

Types of Strategy cited from [Louie \(2017\)](#).

Table 2*Rote Learning vs. Meaningful Learning*

Rote Learning	Meaningful learning
CP: Remember ACP: Recognizing, Recalling	CP: Remember ACP: recognizing, recalling
Goal: Retention	CP: Understand ACP: interpreting, exemplifying, classifying, summarizing, inferring, comparing, explaining
	CP: Apply ACP: executing, implementing
	CP: Analyze ACP: differentiating, organizing, attributing
	CP: Evaluate ACP: checking, critiquing
	CP: Create ACP: Generating, Planning Producing
	Goal: Transfer

Cited from [Mayer \(2002\)](#).

CP stands for Cognitive Process, while ACP stands for Associated Cognitive Process. Rote learning and meaningful learning are described through the cognitive processes used and the associated cognitive process of the cognitive processes listed. For rote learning, one cognitive process consists of two associated cognitive processes. Meaningful learning uses six cognitive processes and nineteen associated cognitive processes.

References

- Abrams, L. M., Pedulla, J. J., & Madaus, G. F. (2003). Views from the classroom: Teachers' opinions of statewide testing programs. *Theory into Practice, 42*(1), 18-29.
https://doi.org/10.1207/s15430421tip4201_4
- Allday, R. A., & Pakurar, K. (2007). Effects of teacher greetings on student on-task behavior. *Journal of Applied Behavior Analysis, 40*(2), 317-320.
<https://doi.org/10.1901%2Fjaba.2007.86-06>
- Barksdale, C., Peters, M. L., & Corrales, A. (2021). Middle school students' perceptions of classroom climate and its relationship to achievement. *Educational Studies, 47*(1), 84-107. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/03055698.2019.1664411>
- Bature, I. J. (2020). The mathematics teachers shift from the traditional teacher-centered classroom to a more constructivist student-centered epistemology. *Open Access Library Journal, 7*(5), 1-26. <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1106389>
- Birenbaum, M., & Nasser, F. (2006). Ethnic and gender differences in mathematics achievement and in dispositions towards the study of mathematics. *Learning and Instruction, 16*(1), 26-40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2005.12.004>
- Boaler, J. (2016). *Mistakes grow your brain*. Youcubed at Stanford University Graduate School of Education. <https://www.youcubed.org/evidence/mistakes-grow-brain/>
- Bobis, J., Anderson, J., Martin, A., & Way, J. (2011). Student dispositions with respect to mathematics: What current literature says. In J. Beyers (Ed.), *Motivation and disposition: Pathways to learning, 73rd yearbook of the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics* (pp. 1-12). NCTM.
- California Department of Education. (n.d.). *Test results at a glance*. CASPP: California

Assessment of Student Performance and Progress.

<https://caaspp-elpac.cde.ca.gov/caaspp/DashViewReportSB?ps=true&lstTestYear=2021&lstTestType=B&lstGroup=1&lstSubGroup=1&lstSchoolType=A&lstGrade=13&lstCounty=00&lstDistrict=00000&lstSchool=0000000>

Carpenter, T. P., Ansell, E., Franke, M. L., Fennema, E., & Weisbeck, L. (1993). Models of problem solving: a study of kindergarten children's problem-solving processes.

Journal for Research in Mathematics Education, 24(5), 428–441.

<https://doi.org/10.2307/749152>

Chapman, O. (2004). Facilitating peer interactions in learning mathematics: teachers' practical knowledge. *International Group for the Psychology of Mathematics Education*, 2, 191-198.

Chubb, M. (2016, July 31). *Focus on relational understanding*. Thinking Mathematically.

<https://buildingmathematicians.wordpress.com/2016/07/31/focus-on-relational-understanding/>

Clyatt, L. A. (2017). *Evolving student perceptions of mathematical identity: a case study of mindset shift* [Doctoral dissertation, Montana State University-Bozeman, College of Education, Health & Human Development]. Montana State University.

Cook, C. R., et. al. (2018). Positive greetings at the door: Evaluation of a low-cost, high-yield proactive classroom management strategy. *Journal of Positive Behavior Interventions*, 20(3), 149-159. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F1098300717753831>

Daniels, E., & Arapostathis, M. (2005). What do they really want? Student voices and motivation research. *Urban Education*, 40(1), 34-59. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0042085904270421>

Deieso, D. (2016). *Changes in learning environment and students' attitudes and anxiety*

associated with the transition from primary to secondary school mathematics [Doctoral dissertation, Curtin University]. Curtin University.

Dowker, A., Sarkar, A., & Looi, C. Y. (2016). Mathematics anxiety: What have we learned in 60 years?. *Frontiers in psychology*, 79(508), 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.00508>

Dunn, K. E., & Mulvenon, S. W. (2009). A critical review of research on formative assessments: The limited scientific evidence of the impact of formative assessments in education. *Practical Assessment, Research, and Evaluation*, 14(7), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.7275/jg4h-rb87>

Dweck, C. S. (2008). *Mindset: The new psychology of success*. Random House Digital, Inc. https://www.google.com/books/edition/Mindset/ft6U0Ee7_kQC?hl=en&gbpv=0

Ellis, M. (2008). Leaving no child behind yet allowing none too far ahead: Ensuring (in) equity in mathematics education through the science of measurement and instruction. *Teachers College Record*, 110(6), 1330-1356.

Ellis, M. W., & Berry III, R. Q. (2005). The paradigm shift in mathematics education: Explanations and implications of reforming conceptions of teaching and learning. *The Mathematics Educator*, 15(1), 7-17.

Fredricks, J. A., Parr, A. K., Amemiya, J. L., Wang, M. T., & Brauer, S. (2019). What matters for urban adolescents' engagement and disengagement in school: A mixed-methods study. *Journal of Adolescent Research*, 34(5), 491-527. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2016.02.002>

Fredriksen, K., & Rhodes, J. (2004). The role of teacher relationships in the lives of students. *New Directions for Youth Development*, 2004(103), 45-54.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/yd.90>

Gordon, L. (2021, August 20). *California State University courses with high failure and withdrawal rates prompt calls for reform*. EdSource.

<https://edsource.org/2021/did-failing-a-tough-course-delay-your-csu-graduation-join-the-club/659556>

Gordon, L. (2022, January 13). *High calculus failure rates thwart students across CSU*. EdSource.

<https://edsource.org/2022/high-calculus-failure-rates-thwart-students-across-csu/664771>

Grady, M. (2016). Whatever happened to productive disposition? *Mathematics Teaching in the Middle School*, 21(9), 516-518. <https://doi.org/10.5951/mathteachmidscho.21.9.0516>

Gresalfi, M. S. (2009). Taking up opportunities to learn: Constructing dispositions in mathematics classrooms. *The Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 18(3), 327-369.

Gresalfi, M. S., & Cobb, P. (2006). Cultivating students' discipline-specific dispositions as a critical goal for pedagogy and equity. *Pedagogies*, 1(1), 49-57.

https://doi.org/10.1207/s15544818ped0101_8

Gutiérrez, R. (2009). Framing equity: helping students “play the game” and “change the game.” *Teaching for Excellence and Equity in Mathematics*, 1(1), 4-8.

Gutiérrez, R. (2012). Context matters: how should we conceptualize equity in mathematics education? In Herbel-Eisenmann, B., Choppin, J., Wagner, D., Pimm, D. (Eds.), *Equity in Discourse for Mathematics Education* (pp.17-33). Springer.

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-2813-4_2

Hogan, M. P. (2008). The tale of two Noras: How a Yup'ik middle schooler was differently

- constructed as a math learner. *Diaspora, Indigenous, and Minority Education*, 2(2), 90-114. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/15595690801894079>
- Ingram, N. (2013). Mathematical engagement skills. In V. Steinle, L. Ball, & C. Bardini (Eds.), *Mathematics Education Research Group of Australasia*.(pp. 402–409). Melbourne: MERGA.
- Kalambouka, A., Pampaka, M., Omuvwie, M., & Wo, L. (2016). Mathematics dispositions of secondary school students with special educational needs. *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, 16, 701-707. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1471-3802.12204>
- Kennedy, L. (2019, September 13). *How attitude towards math impacts student achievement*. Prodigygame.Com. <https://www.prodigygame.com/main-en/blog/attitude-towards-math/>
- Kilpatrick, J., Swafford, J. and Findell, B. (2001). *Adding it up: Helping children learn mathematics*, National Academy Press, Washington, DC. <https://doi.org/10.17226/9822>
- Kitchen, R., Garcia-Olp, M., & Van Ooyik, J. (2017). Resisting student labeling in this era of testing. *Colorado Mathematics Teacher*, 50(3), 2-6.
- Klem, A. M., & Connell, J. P. (2004). Relationships matter: Linking teacher support to student engagement and achievement. *Journal of School Health*, 74(7), 262-273.
- Louie, N. L. (2017). The culture of exclusion in mathematics education and its persistence in equity-oriented teaching. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 48(5), 488-519. <https://doi.org/10.5951/jresmetheduc.48.5.0488>
- Lubienski, S. T. (2002). A closer look at black-white mathematics gaps: intersections of race and SES in NAEP achievement and instructional practices data. *Journal of Negro Education*, 71(4), 269–287. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3211180>
- Marks, H. M. (2000). Student engagement in instructional activity: Patterns in the elementary,

- middle, and high school years. *American Educational Research Journal*, 37(1), 153-184.
<https://doi.org/10.3102%2F00028312037001153>
- Mayer, R. E. (2002). Rote versus meaningful learning. *Theory into practice*, 41(4), 226-232.
https://doi.org/10.1207/s15430421tip4104_4
- Mistele, J. M., & Louis, R. A. (2011). Exploring the middle school mathematics teacher student relationship. Paper presented at the *American Society for Engineering Education Southeastern Section Annual Conference, Charleston, SC*.
http://se.asee.org/proceedings/ASEE2011/Papers/FP2011lou123_141.PDF
- Moon, T. R., Brighton, C. M., Jarvis, J. M., & Hall, C. J. (2007). State standardized testing programs: Their effects on teachers and students. *National Research Center on the Gifted and Talented*.
- Mullis, I. V., Martin, M. O., Foy, P., & Arora, A. (2012). *TIMSS 2011 international results in mathematics*. International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement.
<https://timssandpirls.bc.edu/timss2011/international-results-mathematics.html>
- Mullis, I. V. S., Martin, M. O., Foy, P., & Hooper, M. (2016). *TIMSS 2015 international results in mathematics*. Retrieved from Boston College, TIMSS & PIRLS International Study Center. <http://timssandpirls.bc.edu/timss2015/international-results/>
- Mullis, I. V. S., Martin, M. O., Foy, P., Kelly, D. L., & Fishbein, B. (2020). *TIMSS 2019 international results in mathematics and science*. Retrieved from Boston College, TIMSS & PIRLS International Study Center.
<https://timssandpirls.bc.edu/timss2019/international-results/>
- National Center on Safe Supportive Learning Environments (NCSSLE). (n.d.). *Engagement*.

AIR.

<https://safesupportivelearning.ed.gov/topic-research/engagement#:~:text=Student%20engagement%20is%20a%20key%20element%20of%20a, and%20participating%20in%20classes%20and%20in%20school%20activities>

National Council of Teachers of Mathematics. (2014). *Principles to actions: Ensuring mathematical success for all*. Reston, VA: National Council of Teachers of Mathematics.

National Council of Teachers of Mathematics. (2000). *Principles and standards for school mathematics*. NCTM.

Nguyen, Cannata, M., & Miller, J. (2018). Understanding student behavioral engagement: Importance of student interaction with peers and teachers. *The Journal of Educational Research, 111*(2), 163–174. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220671.2016.1220359>

Perry, B., & Dockett, S. (2008). Young children's access to powerful mathematical ideas. In L. D. English (Ed.), *Handbook of international research in mathematics education* (2nd ed., pp. 75–108). New York: Routledge.

Pilgrim, T. (2014, May 6). *Negative Teacher-Student Relationships*. Eduflow.

<https://eduflow.wordpress.com/2014/05/06/negative-teacher-student-relationships/#:~:text=It%20is%20counterproductive%20and%20usually,the%20boundaries%20that%20separate%20them>

Prewett, S. L., Bergin, D. A., & Huang, F. L. (2019). Student and teacher perceptions on student-teacher relationship quality: A middle school perspective. *School Psychology International, 40*(1), 66-87. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0143034318807743>

Reyes, M. R., Brackett, M. A., Rivers, S. E., White, M., & Salovey, P. (2012). Classroom

- emotional climate, student engagement, and academic achievement. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 104(3), 700-712. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/a0027268>
- Riling, M., Dietiker, L., Gibson, K., Tukhtakhunov, I., & Ren, C. (2018, January). Factors that influence student mathematical dispositions. In *Proceedings of the 40th annual meeting of the North American Chapter of the International Group for the Psychology of Mathematics Education*. <https://par.nsf.gov/biblio/10084168>
- Roseth, C. J., Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. T. (2008). Promoting early adolescents' achievement and peer relationships: the effects of cooperative, competitive, and individualistic goal structures. *Psychological Bulletin*, 134(2), 223-246. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0033-2909.134.2.223>
- Rumberger, R. W., & Rotermund, S. (2012). The relationship between engagement and high school dropout. In Christenson, S., Reschly, A., Wylie, C. (Eds.) *Handbook of research on student engagement* (pp. 491-513). Springer, Boston, MA. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-2018-7_24
- Shahrill, M. (2013). Review of effective teacher questioning in mathematics classrooms. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(17), 224-231.
- Shim, S. S., Kiefer, S. M., & Wang, C. (2013). Help seeking among peers: The role of goal structure and peer climate. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 106(4), 290-300. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220671.2012.692733>
- Skemp, R. R. (1978). Relational understanding and instrumental understanding. *The Arithmetic Teacher*, 26(3), 9-15.
- Small, M. (2012). *Good questions: Great ways to differentiate mathematics instruction*. Teachers College Press.

- Mathematical Agency Improvement Community (MAIC; n.d.). *Status & mindset interventions*.
<https://www.mathagency.org/status-mindset-resources>
- Trilling, B., & Fadel, C. (2009). *21st century skills: Learning for life in our times*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Turner, J. C., Midgley, C., Meyer, D. K., Gheen, M., Anderman, E. M., Kang, Y., & Patrick, H. (2002). The classroom environment and students' reports of avoidance strategies in mathematics: A multimethod study. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 94*(1), 88-106.
<https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0022-0663.94.1.88>
- Umarji, O., Dicke, A. L., Safavian, N., Karabenick, S. A., & Eccles, J. S. (2021). Teachers caring for students and students caring for math: The development of culturally and linguistically diverse adolescents' math motivation. *Journal of School Psychology, 84*, 32-48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsp.2020.12.004>
- Waller, P. P., & Marzocchi, A. S. (2020). From rules that expire to language that inspires. *Mathematics Teacher: Learning and Teaching PK-12, 113*(7), 544-550.
<https://doi.org/10.5951/MTLT.2019.0178>
- Wang, MT., Hofkens, T. & Ye, F. (2020). Classroom quality and adolescent student engagement and performance in mathematics: a multi-method and multi-informant approach. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence, 49*, 1987–2002. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-020-01195-0>
- Willingham, J. C., Barlow, A. T., Stephens, D. C., Lischka, A. E., & Hartland, K. S. (2021). Mindset regarding mathematical ability in K-12 teachers. *School Science and Mathematics, 121*(4), 234-246. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ssm.12466>
- Zippert, E. L., Eason, S. H., Marshall, S., & Ramani, G. B. (2019). Preschool children's math exploration during play with peers. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology, 65*.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appdev.2019.101072>